

NOTES ON PRIMES SMARANDACHE PROGRESSIONS

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Abstract. In this note we discuss the primes in Smarandache progressions.

For any positive integer n , let p_n denote the n^{th} prime.

For the fixed coprime positive integers a, b , let $P(a, b) = \{ap_n + b\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$. Then $P(a, b)$ is called a Smarandache progression.

In [1, Problem 17], Smarandache posed the following questions:

Questions. How many primes belong to $P(a, b)$?

It would seem that the answers of Smarandache's question is different from pairs (a, b) . We now give some observable examples as follows:

Example 1. If a, b are odd integers, then $ap_n + b$ is an even integer for $n > 1$. It implies that $P(a, b)$ contains at most one prime. In particular, $P(1, 1)$ contains only the prime 3.

Example 2. Under the assumption of twin prime conjecture that there exist infinitely many primes p such that $p+2$ is also a prime, then the progression $P(1, 2)$ contains infinitely

many primes.

Example 3. Under the assumption of Germain prime conjecture that there exist infinitely many primes p such that $2p+1$ is also a prime, then the progression $P(2,1)$ contains infinitely many primes.

Reference

1. F.Smarandache, Only Problems, not Solutions!, Xiquan Pub. House, Phoenix, Chicago, 1990.